

FORMATION OF STUDENTS 'CREATIVE TECHNOLOGY, FOLK CRAFT SKILLS IN TECHNOLOGY COURSES

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ABSTRACT

Integrated curricula integrate side-by-side courses around a long subject and idea, which helps students to think creatively. However, integrated courses are designed for the vast majority of people, and one of the subjects is not so much for someone as it is for others. To solve this problem, in order to meet the needs of students in this or that course, schools organize in-depth courses in individual subjects.

Relevance of the topic: Changes in the field of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan are recognized by the world community as one of the key factors in ensuring the future of our country. In turn, the National Program of Personnel Training, as well as the seven principles of the development strategy "Initiative - the path to development" and the advanced innovative developments of each gifted student identified in it, the most common problems and solutions to them. with a focus on upbringing. On this basis, the effective organization of the preparation of students for creative activities is an important factor in ensuring the success of educational reforms.

In our country, which is gaining a worthy place in the world community on the basis of democratic principles, in all forms of education, the circle is considered an important factor in ensuring the freedom of the student. At the current stage of educational reform, the issue of educating a

free-thinking person is becoming more and more important. The main idea and content of our national model of education in this regard is reflected in the "National Training Program". [A.1.; 2.; 3;].

Problems and solutions. The formation of knowledge, skills and competencies in folk crafts is important in the development of creative activity of students in the process of organizing technology classes, as well as extracurricular activities of secondary school students. As a result of the reforms, the transition of schools to work in new conditions places high demands on the activity of teachers, the content and level of their professional and pedagogical training, and the improvement of their knowledge. The relevance of the research work is the development of methods for the development of students' creative activity on the basis of folk crafts in the organization of extracurricular activities on

the basis of educational reforms implemented in our country.

It is known that teaching methods are the subject of coordination of the pedagogical process, which consists of the teacher's activity with students to achieve certain goals, "what?", "To whom?", "What?" and "how much?" serves to address the need for training. Therefore, the activation of students' cognitive activities in the educational process, the choice of forms and methods used for their independent, creative thinking will be effective in further improving the training of personnel. For this reason, a lot of research is being done to improve teaching. Among other subjects, in technology education classes, students must acquire a certain amount of knowledge, skills and abilities.

In secondary schools, advanced, experienced, creative teachers use non-traditional types of lessons, such as tests, seminars, conferences, competitions, tests, theatrical lessons, which meet the requirements of modern lessons. Conducting classes on labor education in such a non-traditional way has a significant impact on the formation of students' creativity, inquisitiveness and ability to think independently. The study of the work carried out in this field, the development of scientific and methodological conclusions, the development of students' interest in the study of theoretical and practical lessons on labor education, the development of this method, the achievement of high efficiency in the process of practical work. At the same time, it shows the urgency of the case.

The urgency of the problem under study is that the National Program provides for a nine-year general secondary and three-year specialized secondary vocational

education, as well as a multi-layered education based on the abilities and capabilities of students. It is planned to fill educational institutions with specially trained qualified teaching staff and create a competitive environment in their work. However, the methodological framework for the implementation of these tasks has not been sufficiently developed. In solving such methodological problems, it is important to develop special methods for the implementation of lessons and other activities in general secondary education. Given the relevance and importance of the above issues in the process of general secondary education in pedagogical research, as well as the fact that technology education is not sufficiently developed in the theory and methodology of teaching, the subject of our research is was. [A.3., 4;].

Object of research : places for the formation of knowledge and skills in folk crafts in the organization of technology education classes and circles in secondary schools.

of research : the content, methods and forms of technology education lessons in grades 5-7 of general secondary schools were obtained.

The purpose of the research : to develop and implement a methodology for the formation of knowledge and skills of students in folk arts classes in technology education.

Research objectives : In order to achieve the set goals and confirm the research hypothesis, the following tasks were identified:

- Analysis of the theoretical basis for the development of students' skills in folk crafts in the process of technology education and circle activities;

- Conducting surveys to determine the interest and abilities of young people in folk crafts;
- Identify the factors that ensure interdisciplinary relevance in the process of conducting labor education classes and classes;
- Substantiate the methodological aspects of the development of creative activity of students in the process of technology education in folk crafts;
- Development of technology for the development of creative abilities of students through the project method.

Research method : study and analysis of scientific and methodological literature on the research topic, including dissertations; to monitor the organization of technology education classes in secondary schools, to conduct interviews with school teachers, teachers and students, to conduct surveys; to study school documents and students' work, to conduct pedagogical experiments on the use of traditional and non-traditional methods of teaching in technology lessons and classes, to analyze the results on the basis of mathematical and statistical methods.

Theoretical and practical significance of the research results:

1. The conditions for the organization of technology education classes are determined.

2. Theoretical bases of formation of knowledge and skills of pupils on national handicrafts from labor education are created.

3. A methodology for developing students' knowledge and skills in folk crafts in technology education classes will be developed.

Scientific novelty:

1. On the basis of the requirements of the educational reforms implemented in the Republic, it was determined that in the lessons of technology education in grades V-VII, the study of folk crafts is organically linked on the basis of circles.

2. The importance of folk crafts in technology education classes.

3. Development of theoretical and methodological bases for the selection and application of modern pedagogical technology methods that are relevant to the content of educational work on the types of technology education lessons.

4. Development of methodological guidelines and recommendations for the selection and application of modern pedagogical technology methods in the lessons of technology education, relevant to the content of educational work on folk crafts.

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